

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ СОҒЛИҚНИ САҚЛАШ ВАЗИРЛИГИ
ТОШКЕНТ ТИББИЁТ АКАДЕМИЯСИ

2024

2011 йилдан чиқа бошлаган

TOSHKENT TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI
AХВОРОТНОМАСИ

ВЕСТНИК

ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ АКАДЕМИИ

SPECIAL EDITION

Only English "ADVANCES IN MEDICAL
RESEARCH AND PRACTICE
CONFERENCE"

Тошкент

Выпуск набран и сверстан на компьютерном издательском комплексе

редакционно-издательского отдела Ташкентской медицинской академии

Начальник отдела: М. Н. Аслонов

Редактор русского текста: О.А. Козлова

Редактор узбекского текста: М.Г. Файзиева

Редактор английского текста: А.Х. Жураев

Компьютерная корректура: З.Т. Алюшева

Учредитель: Ташкентская медицинская академия

Издание зарегистрировано в Ташкентском Городском управлении печати и информации

Регистрационное свидетельство 02-00128

Журнал внесен в список, утвержденный приказом № 201/3 от 30 декабря 2013года

реестром ВАК в раздел медицинских наук

Рукописи, оформленные в соответствии

с прилагаемыми правилами, просим направлять

по адресу: 100109, Ташкент, ул. Фароби, 2,

Главный учебный корпус ТМА,

4-й этаж, комната 444.

Контактный телефон: 214 90 64

e-mail: rio-tma@mail.ru

rio@tma.uz

Формат 60x84 1/8. Усл. печ. л. 9,75.

Гарнитура «Cambria».

Тираж 150.

Цена договорная.

Отпечатано на ризографе редакционно-издательского отдела ТМА.

100109, Ташкент, ул. Фароби, 2.

Вестник ТМА 2024

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ

Главный редактор

проф. А.К. Шадманов

Заместитель главного редактора

проф. О.Р.Тешаев

Ответственный секретарь

проф. Ф.Х.Иноятова

ЧЛЕНЫ РЕДАКЦИОННОЙ КОЛЛЕГИИ

акад. Аляви А.Л.

проф. Билалов Э.Н.

проф. Гадаев А.Г.

проф. Жае Вук Чои (Корея)

акад. Каримов Ш.И.

проф. Татьяна Силина (Украина)

акад. Курбанов Р.Д.

проф. Людмила Зуева (Россия)

проф. Метин Онерчи (Турция)

проф. Ми Юн (Корея)

акад. Назыров Ф.Г.

проф. Нажмутдинова Д.К.

проф. Саломова Ф.И.

проф. Саша Трескач (Германия)

проф. Шайхова Г.И.

ЧЛЕНЫ РЕДАКЦИОННОГО СОВЕТА

проф. Акилов Ф.О. (Ташкент)

проф. Аллаева М.Д. (Ташкент)

проф. Хамдамов Б.З. (Бухара)

проф. Ирискулов Б.У. (Ташкент)

проф. Каримов М.Ш. (Ташкент)

проф. Маматкулов Б.М. (Ташкент)

проф. Охунов А.О. (Ташкент)

проф. Парпиева Н.Н. (Ташкент)

проф. Рахимбаева Г.С. (Ташкент)

проф. Хамраев А.А. (Ташкент)

проф. Холматова Б.Т. (Ташкент)

проф. Шагазатова Б.Х. (Ташкент)

Herald TMA 2024

EDITORIAL BOARD

Editor in chief

prof. A.K. Shadmanov

Deputy Chief Editor

prof. O.R. Teshayev

Responsible secretary

prof. F.Kh. Inoyatova

EDITORIAL TEAM

academician Alyavi A.L.

prof. Bilalov E.N.

prof. Gadaev A.G.

prof. Jae Wook Choi (Korea)

academician Karimov Sh.I.

prof. Tatyana Silina (Ukraine)

academician Kurbanov R.D. prof. Lyudmila Zueva (Russia)

prof. Metin Onerc (Turkey)

prof. Mee Yeun (Korea)

prof. Najmutdinova D.K.

prof. Salomova F.I.

prof. Sascha Treskatch (Germany)

prof. Shaykhova G.I.

EDITORIAL COUNCIL

DSc. Abdullaeva R.M.

prof. Akilov F.O. (Tashkent)

prof. Allaeva M.D. (Tashkent)

prof. Khamdamov B.Z. (Bukhara)

prof. Iriskulov B.U. (Tashkent)

prof. Karimov M.Sh. (Tashkent)

prof. Mamatkulov B.M. (Tashkent)

prof. Okhunov A.A. (Tashkent)

prof. Parpieva N.N. (Tashkent)

prof. Rakhimbaeva G.S. (Tashkent)

prof. Khamraev A.A. (Tashkent)

prof. Kholmatova B.T. (Tashkent)

prof. Shagazatova B.X. (Tashkent)

*Journal edited and printed in the computer of Tashkent
Medical Academy editorial department*

Editorial board of Tashkent Medical Academy

Head of the department: M.N. Aslonov

Russian language editor: O.A. Kozlova

Uzbek language editor: M.G. Fayzieva

English language editor: A.X. Juraev

Corrector: Z.T. Alyusheva

Organizer: Tashkent Medical Academy

*Publication registered in editorial and information
department of Tashkent city*

Registered certificate 02-00128

*Journal approved and numbered under the order 201/3 from 30 of
December 2013 in Medical Sciences department OF SUPREME ATTESTATION*

COMMISSION

COMPLETED MANUSCRIPTS PLEASE SEND following address:

*2-Farobiy street, 4 floor room 444. Administration building of TMA.
Tashkent. 100109, Toshkent, ul. Farobi, 2, TMA bosh o'quv binosi, 4-qavat,
444-xona.*

Contact number: 71- 214 90 64

e-mail: rio-tma@mail.ru. rio@tma.uz

Format 60x84 1/8. Usl. printer. l. 9.75.

Listening means «Cambria».

Circulation 150.

Negotiable price

Printed in TMA editorial and publisher department risograph

2 Farobiy street, Tashkent, 100109.

Conclusions: In the comparative aspect of the control and experimental groups, a delay in the development of hepatocyte cellular structures was noted. For further and in-depth study, it is advisable to conduct IHC study using markers of proliferative and apoptotic activity.

ANALYSIS OF THE INDICATORS OF HOSPITALIZED INCIDENCE OF OSTEOCHONDROSIS OF THE SPINE

Umurzakova D.A.

School of public health, Tashkent medical academy

Relevance. The vast material accumulated through the development of MRI and CT has shown that the term “osteocondrosis” hides many pathologies, both degenerative and inflammatory. Statistics show a high incidence of osteochondrosis and no tendency to decrease it. According to the US National Center for Health Statistics, people under the age of 45 are more likely to limit their activities due to persistent back or neck pain. Spinal pathology is the fifth most common cause of hospitalization and the third most common cause of surgical treatment. By gender distribution, the prevalence of the disease is higher among women than among men. In addition, back and neck pain limit vital functions, reduce the quality of life of patients, disorganize not only the functional state of the body, but also change the psyche and behavior of people.

Aim. To study age-sex characteristics, social status and occupation in hospitalized patients as risk factors for the development of spinal osteochondrosis.

Materials and methods: To study age and gender characteristics, social status and occupation as risk factors for spinal osteochondrosis in hospitalized patients, 2,511 case histories of patients of the department of vertebrology diagnosed with OS were studied in the archive of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics. The analysis of statistical data was carried out in the Statistica 10.0 application software package.

Results. The analysis of statistical data showed that the majority of hospitalized patients with Osteochondrosis of the spine are people of working age, since their average age was 56.6 ± 0.3 years and did not significantly change during the study period. The minimum age of hospitalized patients with osteochondrosis is 16 years, the maximum is 91 years. When comparing the characteristics of patients depending on gender, it was found that the ages of men and women hospitalized for spinal osteochondrosis differ, the average age of women was 5.8 years higher than that of men ($p < 0.001$) (58.5 ± 0.3 and 52.7 ± 0.5 years, respectively). The analysis of the place of residence revealed the predominance of patients living in rural areas. Depending on the type of activity, the hospitalized patients were distributed as follows: the share of employees was 16%, workers - 12%. At the same time, a large number (68%) of unemployed among patients with osteochondrosis draws attention. Professional composition: the main part of the male group consists of drivers, farmers and workers. An analysis of the professional composition of the group of employees hospitalized with osteochondrosis revealed the following features: on average, 34.3 ± 2.3 cases of hospitalization occurred among teachers. Among the teachers, there was a significant predominance of women ($39.2 \pm 2.9\%$) over men ($24.2 \pm 3.8\%$) ($p < 0.0005$). Despite the fact that more than half (61%) of the unemployed patients (1,690 people) were pensioners, a large percentage of them were unemployed people of working age and non-retirement age (39%). The main contingent of unemployed people are women.

Conclusion. The prevalence of spinal osteochondrosis is significantly influenced by age and occupational factors. If in men, the occurrence and development of Osteochondrosis were greatly influenced by professional factors and occupation (sedentary, sedentary lifestyle), then in women, metabolic changes associated with age and menopause prevailed.

THE ROLE OF ENDOCRINOLOGY IN REGULATING HORMONAL IMBALANCES AND MANAGING ENDOCRINE DISORDERS

Yuldashev B.A

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent Uzbekistan

Introduction. Endocrinology is the study of the endocrine system, its hormone-secreting glands, and the physiological effects of hormones on the human body. Hormones play a critical role in regulating metabolism, growth, reproduction, and mood. Dysfunction in the endocrine system, whether due to glandular abnormalities or hormonal imbalances, can lead to a wide array of diseases and conditions such as diabetes, thyroid disorders, and adrenal insufficiency. This thesis explores the mechanisms by which the endocrine system influences health and how endocrinologists diagnose, manage, and treat hormonal disorders.

Aim. The primary aim of this thesis is to:

1. Investigate the role of the endocrine system in maintaining homeostasis and normal bodily functions.
2. Examine the common disorders associated with endocrine dysfunction and their impact on human health.

Nazarova M.M., Inoyatova F. KH., Rabimova Z.SH. KETOGENIC DIET IN TREATMENT OF METABOLIC SYNDROME	23
Rabimova Z.SH., Azizova D.M., Inoyatova F.KH., Nazarova M.M. NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE AND ITS TREATMENT METHODS	24
Ulmasbekov A.K. THE USE OF BIOIMPEDANCE ANALYSIS OF BODY COMPOSITION TO DETERMINE THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE BODY IN COMORBID PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME.	25
Jabborova M.I, Irisqulov B.U EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY IN RATS USING CYSTATIN C.	25
Azizova F.Kh., Ubaidullaeva M.A. MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE LIVER IN RATS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH INDUCED DIABETES MELLITUS	26
Umurzakova D.A. ANALYSIS OF THE INDICATORS OF HOSPITALIZED INCIDENCE OF OSTEOCHONDROSIS OF THE SPINE	27
Yuldashev B.A. THE ROLE OF ENDOCRINOLOGY IN REGULATING HORMONAL IMBALANCES AND MANAGING ENDOCRINE DISORDERS	27
Yusupova D.Y., Muratov F.H. THE EFFECT OF ANTICONVULSANTS ON THE BONE SYSTEM	28
Ergashev U.Y., Iriskulov B.U., Zokhirov A.R. CONTEMPORARY MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC FOOT SYNDROME	28
Sharipova B.A., Tursunov X.Z, Xoliyeva N.X. PANCREAS PATHOMORPHOLOGY IN COVID-19	29
Khashimov F.F. , Kakhramanova N. OZONE THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ECZEMA	30
Isaeva N.Z., Muxamedjanov A. X., Mirzayeva A.H. Muftaydinova Sh. K. INFLUENCE OF TUGLISIDE ON PROTEIN BIOSYNTHESIS IN RAT LIVER	31
Mukhamedjanov A.Kh. Muxamedjanov A. X., Muftaydinova Sh. K. HELIOTRIN MODEL OF TOXIC HEPATITIS	31
Nekova K.Kh., Dusmatov U.A., Khasanova D.A. THERAPEUTIC ROLE OF SPECIALIZED AMINO ACIDS IN THE TREATMENT OF SEPSIS	31
Nuraliyeva Zarnigor Saminjon qizi. SYNTHESIS OF BILE ACIDS FROM CHOLESTEROL AND THE ASSOCIATION WITH THE ENZYME 7-ALPHA HYDROXYLASE IN EXPERIMENTAL ATHEROSCLEROSIS	32
Ashurov S.R., Dadabaeva N.A., Mirzalieva A.A. DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR SYSTEMIC LUPUS ERYTHEMATOSUS (SLE)	33
Parpibaeva D.A., Musaeva M.A. THE VALUE OF ELASTOMETRY INDICATORS AT THE BASIC STAGE OF TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE	34
Parpibaeva D.A., Musaeva M.A., NON-INVASIVE METHODS FOR DIAGNOSIS OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE	34
Dadabaeva N.A., Mirzalieva A.A., Sultonova S.A. PERCUSSION: FROM THE FIRST BLOW TO THE DIAGNOSIS OF LUNG DISEASES	35
Gadaev, A. G., Salaeva M.S. COMORBIDITY OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND RENAL DYSFUNCTION: RISK FACTORS AND COMORBIDITIES	36
Gulyamova Sh.S., Parpibaeva D.A., Salaeva M.S., Salimova N.D. EFFECTIVE CONTROL AND DISPENSERIZATION OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION BY GROUP TRAINING OF PATIENTS IN POLYCLINICAL CONDITIONS	36
Gulyamova Sh.S., Parpibaeva D.A., Salaeva M.S., Salimova N.D. EFFECTIVE CONTROL AND DISPENSARY SUPERVISION OF HYPERTONIC DISEASE IN THE CONDITIONS OF A FAMILY POLYCLINIC	37
Salaeva M.S., Parpibaeva D.A., Gulyamova Sh.S., Salimova N.D. DETERMINATION OF THE PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF SOCIAL FACTORS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE	38
Tashpulatova M.M., Nabieva D.A. CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF GOUTY ARTHRITIS WITH GENDER PECULIARITIES	38
Tashpulatova M.M., Nabieva D.A. ASYMPTOMATIC HYPERURICEMIA AND BONE TISSUE CONDITION IN FEMALE PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME	39
Tashpulatova M.M., Nabiyeva D.A. ANALYSIS OF ADHERENCE TO HYPOURICEMIC THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH GOUT	39
Nabieva D.A., Tashpulatova M.M. ESTIMATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ESTROGEN DEFICIENCY AND GOUT IN WOMEN	40
Mo'minjonov A.A., Mamatojiyev Sh.A., Sagdullayeva M.A., Yuldashev A.N. PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN BORN WITH HEART DEFECTS	41
Mo'minjonov A.A., Mamatojiyev Sh.A., Sagdullayeva M.A., Yuldashev A.N. DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS IN CHILDREN.	41
Zokirova A.M MODERN APPROACHES TO CLINIC AND DIAGNOSTICS OF PATIENTS WITH CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA SYNDROME	42